

PROCEDIN

Building Procurement Capability for Embedding and Driving Innovation

D3.3

Best Practice Compilation with Navigation Decision Interface

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PROCEDIN

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
UA IRPP	Urban Agenda on Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement
WP	Work Package
POI	Procurement of Innovation

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

PROCEDIN is all about ‘networking networks’.¹ A core premise of the project is that truly embedding innovation procurement into everyday procurement practice relies on a fundamental (re)orientation towards public procurement as a lever for strategic, systemic change. This relies on building capability within key groups in the ecosystem, but also building collective capacity for genuine collaboration at multiple levels – starting with specific innovations, contracts, and projects, through leadership in organisations (buyer and vendor), local innovation ecosystems, and on to the pan-European network of actors working in a wide variety of ways on their shared goal of nurturing innovation through procurement. By centring on the very successful Urban Agenda on Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement (UA IRPP) partnership and connecting this with platform organisations already successfully serving vendors across and beyond Europe (F6S and Tenderio), PROCEDIN leverages existing strengths and promotes new links.

In line with this premise, training materials are not being developed from scratch. A deliberate decision has been made to further enhance the resources already designed and successfully launched by the UA IRPP partnership, to stimulate collaboration and co-creation and to guarantee quality and ease of access. This means that for this deliverable, PROCEDIN contributes profoundly to the E-Learning module² developed by the UA IRPP on public procurement, by enhancing the module of the legal framework (Figure 1).

Figure 1. E-Learning UA IRPP: Legal Framework Module, Introduction

This E-Learning module presents a toolbox with different legal aspects that will help on how to achieve more with public procurement. It provides easy ways to use the different legal instruments and, thus, also how to stay within the lines of the legal framework. It presents criteria through infographics and best practices that help procurers find the right instrument for their procurement.

¹ The background of this deliverable (D3.3) corresponds with the background of deliverable 3.1, as their development is based on the same vision and values to stimulate collaboration and co-creation.

² E-Learning modules Urban Agenda Partnership on Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement: <https://uapp.maester.com>

1.2 Aim

This deliverable, D3.3, aims to address the challenges that procurers and SMEs face in procurement procedures, regarding the legal framework of innovation and innovative procurement. The legal aspects of these procedures and the additional legal instruments are often experienced as highly complicated. In addition to D3.1, which encompassed the enhancement of legal roadmaps of complex legal tools and procedures, by creating distinct steps within the different procedures and instruments and portraying them in a clear and visualised manner, D3.3 clarifies these procedures and instruments by adding best practices to each of them.

This deliverable includes four main actions:

1. **Accumulation of best practices per legal procedure and instrument:** best practices illustrate the theoretical steps described in the roadmaps. By including best practices to these roadmaps, the steps become more tangible and practical. It gives end-users concrete insights on how to perform a particular procedure or use an instrument, making it more relatable to their own projects. Moreover, the structuring of best practices by the instrument applied (instead of the subject of the procurement) enables the contracting authorities to choose and adapt the approach they need for the award of the public procurement, regardless of what type of good or service it concerns. The gathered best practices are added to the E-Learning module of the partnership of the UA IRPP.
2. **Enhancing the representation of the best practices:** the representation of the best practices is important for a couple of reasons. First, representation influences the readability of the information and consequently the comprehension or incomprehension of the information. Secondly, if the information is represented in an attractive way, it captures the attention of end-users. Easy-readable and attractive represented information helps motivating procurers to use the given information.
3. **Enhancing the decision-making model:** a decision-making model has to be clear and well-organised. Enhancing the existing decision-making model sheds light on the path procurers have to take for their own procurement project within the large quantity of information that exists on procurement procedures and instruments.
4. **Developing an interface to navigate between the existing best practices:** in order to avoid just adding information to the already large pile of existing information, it is important to develop a navigation interface. The goal of the interface is to assist end-users in navigating among the best practices. PROCEDIN presents this interface on the PROCEDIN website. The section of the E-Learning module of the partnership of the UA IRPP in which the best practices are presented will also include a click-through to this navigation interface, adding to the accessibility of the best practices.

By interlinking the E-Learning module of the partnership of the UA IRPP and the navigation interface on the PROCEDIN website, an extensive network of stakeholders is reached. At the same time, it promotes the PROCEDIN website and thus the developed resource bank for buyers and suppliers (D1.1 and D1.2) and the database of European education provision (D4.1).

1.3 Objectives Work Package 3

The actions described above add to both of the objectives (Table 1) of work package 3 (WP3). The legal framework of the network of the partnership of the UA IRPP is used by enhancing existing information in the E-Learning module and adding new information to it. At the same time, the improved roadmaps and best practices are used in the trainings given by the consortium partners on

legal framework topics. Through these actions, the project thus leverages existing resources and connects networks to enhance and mobilise POI motivation, knowledge, and skills.

Objective 1: DEPLOY LEGAL FRAMEWORK	To deploy the legal framework of innovation and innovative procurement by advancing and developing the legal framework of the existing network of the Urban Agenda Partnership on Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement.
Objective 2: PROVIDE LEGAL ASSISTANCE	Providing legal assistance by using this advanced and developed legal framework, by organising webinars on legal framework topics.

Table 1. Introduction: Objectives WP3

2 Methodology

This section discusses respectively the execution of the four main actions as outlined in paragraph 1.2.

2.1 Accumulation of Best Practices

Before the implementation of WP3, the E-Learning module only included three best practices concerning the legal framework.. Therefore, the consortium partners have gathered new best practices that correspond with the legal procedures and instruments that are displayed in the E-Learning module on the legal framework of the partnership of the UA IRPP. These best practices were not only contributed by the consortium partners, but were also gathered from partners’ networks, social media channels, the UA IRPP, and through inquiries made during conferences and events. A comprehensive overview of all procedures and instruments can be found in Table 2.

Procedure	Instrument
Competitive Dialogue	Market Consultation
Innovation Partnership	Total Cost of Ownership
Pre-Commercial Procurement	Award Below Threshold
	Functional Specification
	Innovation During the Contract Period
	Human Centred Design
	Testing Ground

Table 2. Content: Procedures & Instruments

To ensure a coherent set of best practices, general questions (Table 3) regarding each best practice were asked. These questions made it possible to create a structured and well-organised format for each best practice, presenting the most important information of a project in one glance.

Questions per best practice
1. Can you give a short description of the project?
2. What is the amount of the procurement?

3. What legal framework has been used and why?
4. What are the learned lessons; do's & don'ts?
5. What are the award criteria?
6. What are the benefits of this procurement?

Table 3. Content: Contextual Questions

2.2 Representation Best Practices

Before the execution of the tasks related to this deliverable, the three best practices that were shown in the E-Learning module contained a bulk of information and were presented in a dense and plain text. Figure 2 illustrates the first part of a practical example and how the information was represented at the time.

Choose the right process

1.4 A practical example: Gabrovo municipality

Gabrovo Municipality (Bulgaria): Execution of energy-saving service, modernisation and repair of street lighting in the town of Gabrovo by a contract, using the method of a guaranteed result.

Amount of the procurement in euro's: €1,958,000 euro including VAT

Description of the innovation project: Replacement of the existing street (road) lighting with new energy efficient LED luminaries. Gabrovo street lighting is sufficient for now but, apart from LED luminaries that have already been used in certain projects, they are still sodium-vapor lamps and do not meet standard of the EN 13201-3:2005. The Gabrovo municipality system for managing street (road) lightening also has to be developed and upgraded (or replaced) with a new modern one, as the market engagement and consultation show that the modern systems for managing (or replaced) with a new modern one, as the market engagement and consultation show that the modern systems for managing and monitoring are able to realise a good percentage of savings. The third problem with the street (road) lightening that needs solving is managing the electricity cable network and infrastructure. The project is aimed to attract private funding, and to guarantee the result of the investment. The project must be efficient, so that the initial investment will be repaid from the savings in energy.

What was the aim of using innovation procurement for this purchase: The competitive dialogue procedure was chosen, as it gives the participants opportunities to offer different solutions. This is the main issue in the procedure with guaranteed result (ESCO) from our point of view - to give full freedom to the participants to bid and propose the solution. The contractor is in charge of the whole system and infrastructure during the contract (around 10 years), for which they are responsible and guarantee the achievement of the set goals. We have seen tenders for ESCO contracts in Bulgaria in which concrete requirements for the used luminaries are set, by way of technical specifications. But we feel

Figure 2. Representation Best Practices: Old Template

Enhancing the representation of the best practices entailed both actualising the text as well as boosting the depiction of the text. To accomplish this goal, a template was designed, suitable for each best practice (Figure 3).

GABROVO MUNICIPALITY

Practical Example Streetlighting in the town of Gabrovo

THE PROJECT

Replacement of the existing street (road) lighting with new energy efficient LED luminaries.

- Apart from LED luminaries that have already been used in certain projects, they are still sodium-vapor lamps and do not meet standard of the EN 15201-3:2005.
- The Gabrovo municipality system for managing street (road) lightening also has to be developed and upgraded (or replaced) with a new modern one, as the market engagement and consultation show that the modern systems for managing and monitoring are able to realise a good percentage of savings.
- The third problem with the street (road) lightening that needs solving is managing the electricity cable network and infrastructure.

The project is aimed to attract private funding, and to guarantee the result of the investment. The project must be efficient, so that the initial investment will be repaid from the savings in energy.

Amount of the procurement in euro's: €1.958.000 including VAT

COMPETITIVE DIALOGUE

- The competitive dialogue procedure was chosen, as it gives the participants opportunities to offer different solutions.
- The competitive dialogue procedure offers a chance for the public authority to see the offered decision in advance and to create a better partnership relationship with the tenderers (future contractor).
- Another reason was that by using a dialogue it is easier to explain the actual situation and needs of the public authority. In this case, the issue was that we have difficulties in presenting the exact condition of the cable network, needed to find the best solution for who and what responsibilities are in place for the maintenance and operation of the cable network and staircase infrastructure.

IMPORTANT CONDITIONS

Most important in choosing this approach was the ability to attract private funds. We used the competitive dialogue to find the best technology. Essentially, we aimed to receive an offer how to place luminaries more efficiently (i.e. more luminaries with less power or fewer luminaries with more power), and to give a chance to the economic operators to offer new technology for power supply etc. This procedure allows tenderers to offer the managing and monitoring system with different resources for the organization of the maintenance from the contractor.

AWARD CRITERIA

Price - 30%; Guaranteed amount of reduced CO2 emissions - 15%; saved energy - 25,2%; level of the automatic location of a damaged luminary. The evaluation of the project's effectiveness is performed according to the indicator "Net present value" - 14,3%.

BENEFITS OF THIS INNOVATION PROCUREMENT

- The solutions come from tenderers and the result of it is guaranteed, as the tenderer is in charge to design and implement the project. The payment is bound to the reached level of the offered result.
- Important is the result, not the technical execution.
- We created a good partnership with the tenderers and developed/improved the result of the project on a dialogue level, comparing the different solutions.

Figure 3. Representation Best Practices: New Template

The template has been divided in manageable pieces of text, introduced by a clear heading to indicate the content of the piece of text. It contains a short introduction to the project and the used procedure/instrument accompanied by an explanation of why that specific procedure/instrument was used. Furthermore, it shows important conditions of the project that relate to the legal procedure/instrument, the award criteria, and the benefits experience by using that certain procedure/instrument. Facts about the project and the explanation of the used procedure/instrument function as insights on how to put it into practice. The benefits of the innovation procurement function to motivate the end-user to put it into practice in their own procurement project. The template provides an attractive way of providing information to the end-user, improving both user-friendliness and comprehension of the information.

The consortium of PROCEDIN, in collaboration with other European networks, put a lot of effort into enriching the best practices database with new practical examples of successful use of legal framework of public procurement of innovation. Thanks to these efforts, 25 best practices were initially added to the E-learning modules and the PROCEDIN database, making the best practices available at both sites (Figure 4, Figure 5).

This page provides an extensive list of enriching and informative resources related to both responsible/sustainable procurement and innovation procurement in the public sector. Select filters and find more about best practices, legal frameworks, tools & training providers and/or filter by country, to find more resources specific to the selected country.

Public Resource

Country

Best practices and case study resources

All Items

How Lithuania fast-tracked green procurement

In 2020, only 5% of Lithuania’s public procurement spending by value used green criteria that favor environmentally friendly products and services. The government wanted to shift that to 100% by 2023. It is currently developing a methodology to calculate the impact of

Reuse and refurbishment of furniture through circular economy procurement

Public Health Wales adopted a new mindset when moving office in 2016, and instead sought suppliers who could reuse and remanufacture as much already owned furniture as possible. PHW released a tender for the design of office space and supply of furniture in April

Framework agreement for zero-emission vehicles

Pursuing its objective of having a zero-emission vehicle fleet by 2015, the City of Oslo has concluded a framework agreement to replace a thousand cars and vans with environmentally friendly options in the years to come. A range of pre-procurement activities were

Figure 4: Best practices in the PROCEDIN Database. Accessible via: [Buyers for Innovation – PROCEDIN](#)

Urban Agenda - Public Procurement

Welcome to the online modules of the Urban Agenda Public Procurement.

Watch the introduction first to get started.
Click the icons or the colored parts of the circle to go to that module.

▶ Watch the introduction

Figure 5: The E-learning Modules of the UA IRPP. Accessible via: [Urban Agenda - Public Procurement \(maester.com\)](#)

In the last months, an effort to diversify the countries contributing to best practices has been initiated. The best practices that have been found were mostly added under the ‘More Good Practices’ tab. Each best practice was added with a short description about the procurement and its impact and a link to the source, so if needed users can get an elaborate explanation of the example as can be seen in Figure 6. At the moment, the total number of best practices has reached 48 with the current distribution displayed in Figure 7.

More Good Practices
Innovation Partnership

Procurement of a quantum computer – FINLAND

The aim of the acquisition was to form an innovation partnership for the development and delivery of a quantum computer. Quantum computers are expected to be able to solve problems that are impossible for today's computers with their unprecedented computing power. Potential future applications include accurate modelling of viruses and drugs and the design of completely new materials, which is impossible with current methods.

[Procurement of a quantum computer – Case VTT | Hankintakeino.fi](#)

Kotidigi integration platform, combining home and remote care technologies – FINLAND

The Kotidigi platform has been acquired through an innovation partnership procedure, which enables the development of a new solution together with selected innovation partners. As the population ages, the demand for home services and devices increases. With Kotidigi, the data collected by devices

Figure 6. Example of the good practices under the ‘More Good Practices’ tab

Figure 7. Current Balance of Good Practices per Country and Instrument/Procedure

2.3 Decision-Making Model

The E-Learning module of the partnership of the UA IRPP on the legal framework contained a decision-making model for both the legal procedures as well as the legal instruments. Such a decision-making

model was necessary to assist public authorities in choosing the appropriate legal tool or procedure for their specific situation. However, for the first model the line of thought was hard to follow, without sufficient knowledge of the legal procedures beforehand. The second model missed some of the instruments, like market consultation (D3.1). Both were not quite readable as well. Thus, they have been updated in terms of content and in terms of quality, accessibility, and attractiveness.

Figure 8. Decision-Making Model: Old Decision-Making Model Legal Procedures

Figure 9. Decision-Making Model: Old Decision-Making Model Legal Instruments

2.3.1 Decision-Making Model: Legal Procedures

The decision-making model for the legal procedures has been transformed to a decision-making tree in which the end-user can answer a question, from where their answer will lead to a follow-up question and eventually to which legal procedure fits their project best. Figure 6 and Figure 7 both illustrate a question asked in the decision-tree, which leads the end-user with their answer to the next question.

Figure 10. Decision-Making Model: Legal Procedures: New Model, Example 1 Question

Figure 11. Decision-Making Model: Legal Procedures: New Model, Example 2 Question

The new decision-making model for legal procedures is easy-to-use in terms of readability and comprehension. Important aspects of the different procedures have been split up into questions that together define which procedure is the most applicable to the situation of the end-user. The end-users do not have to look for the conditions themselves anymore, as they are now in pieces presented to them. Figure 8 depicts the full new model of the decision-making tree.

Figure 12. Decision-Making Model: Legal Procedures: New Model, Complete

2.3.2 Decision-Making Model: Legal Instruments

The decision-making model for legal instruments (Figure 9) has been designed based on the phase of a procurement procedure.

Figure 13. Decision-Making Model: Legal Instruments: New Model, Complete

The model enables end-users to identify which legal instrument is applicable to which phase of the procedure. The phases are aligned with the amount of effort an instrument involves. This combination allows for a precise consideration by the end-user on which phase is applicable to them and the capacity needed for the legal instrument concerned, leading to an appropriate choice of what legal instrument to use.

2.3.3 Navigation Decision Interface E-Learning Module

In the E-Learning module of the partnership of the UA IRPP, the end-user has the possibility, after following the decision-making models for both the legal procedures as the legal instruments, to select the procedure or process in the menu of the E-Learning module they are interested in. This leads the end-user to the infographic concerning that particular procedure or instrument, accompanying explanations and descriptions. Figure 10 and Figure 11 depict the navigation menus of the E-Learning module.

Figure 14. Navigation Decision Interface E-Learning Module: Choose the Right Instrument

Figure 15. Navigation Decision Interface E-Learning Module: Choose the Right Process

In addition, there are two options for e-learning module users to navigate to more good practices through the interface. One is the option to click through to PROCEDIN database (figure 12), where good practices can be found by region and topic. In the Navigation Decision Interface of the e-module, this is followed by an overview of various good practices by legal process or tool (figure 13).

Figure 16 Click-through link to the PROCEDIN Database

Figure 17 Overview of good practices per legal processes and tools

Figure 18 Overview of the Navigation Decision Interface

2.4 Navigation Interface PROCEDIN

As mentioned in paragraph 1.2, the consortium wanted to avoid that the tasks of WP3 just led to adding information to an already enormous whirlpool of information residing on the internet. Therefore, the consortium partners developed a navigation interface on the PROCEDIN-website for all the best practices (figure 15). This navigation interface enables end-users to select best practices per procedure/instrument and per region. This further facilitates end-users to find best practices related to their own circumstances. The interface thus provides legal assistance to end-users.

Buyers for Innovation

This page provides an extensive list of enriching and informative resources related to both responsible/sustainable procurement and innovation procurement in the public sector. Select filters and find more about best practices, legal frameworks, tools & training providers and/or filter by country, to find more resources specific to the selected country.

Public Resource Country

All Items All Items

Sustainability budget

The sustainability budget is an integral part of the Program Budget of the municipality of Haarlem, directing decisions on resource use and climate policy. Valued at €300 million annually, it emphasizes step-by-step development, integrating sustainability into decision-making. The budget fosters collective responsibility, featuring tools like sustainability memoranda and an Energy Savings Revolving Fund, contributing to Haarlem's commitment to national targets and a quantitatively based

Flanders: Department of Economy, Science & Innovation

We are committed to the ideal mix of economy, science and innovation to guide Flanders to the top of European regions. The EWI Department forms the core within the EWI policy domain and focuses primarily on preparing, monitoring and evaluating policy around the themes of economy, science and innovation.

Energy Transition, Minerals and the Circular Economy

The ongoing energy transition requires a large-scale and accelerated switch to renewable energy generation and the electrification of transportation...

Figure 19 Navigation Interface PROCEDIN

3 Conclusion

By compiling best practices and structuring them through a user-friendly navigation interface, this deliverable contributes to the objectives of WP3: 1) to deploy the legal framework of innovation and innovative procurement by advancing and developing the legal framework of the existing network of the UA IRPP and 2) to provide legal assistance.

This deliverable has not only enhanced the working package but also promotes innovation, simplifies legal procedures, and reduces complexities in procurement of innovation (POI). It offers step-by-step guides to simplify legislative processes, resulting in more user-friendly tools and products. This, in turn, reduces fear and risk aversion associated with POI, thus increasing the adoption of tools related to it. It encourages public authorities to incorporate innovation in procurement, addressing societal challenges effectively.

By gathering best practices from various regions across Europe and considering diverse political, cultural, and environmental perspectives, public authorities can better understand and relate to their own circumstances. The interface allows for easy navigation between these perspectives, making the implementation of POI more accessible in practice.

3.1 Next Steps

To keep the results of the deliverable relevant, the following next steps have been formulated:

- **Continuous updates of the best practices:** best practices will be continuously accumulated and added to the already displayed best practices on the interface of PROCEDIN. This will keep the database up to date and provide end-users with the most recent developments in best practices regarding legal procedures and legal tools.
- **Promoting the E-Learning module:** the E-Learning module will be continuously promoted through the network of the partnership of the UA IRPP. This keeps the end-users aware of procurement of innovation.
- **Promoting the PROCEDIN interface through the E-Learning module:** the E-Learning module will contain a click-through to the interface of PROCEDIN, which will keep the interface being circulated throughout different networks.